

AWARENESS AND USE OF E-RESOURCES BY THE USERS OF THE UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES IN GUJARAT

Vasantray A Chauhan * Dr. Vaishaliben L Bhavsar**

* L.C.Institute of
Technology, Bhandu,
Gujarat, India

** Librarian
Anand Education College,
Anand, Gujarat, India.

QR Code

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates awareness and use of E-Resources in University libraries of Gujarat. The paper also discusses the need to increase awareness of e-resources subscribed by university libraries. Results study revealed that the majority of the respondents were not aware of e-resources. It was discovered that the main purpose of using e-resources by the users is for research and teaching. Majority of the respondents indicated that they use e-resources at university library and departmental libraries. The overall opinion of the library respondents was that only one third users are fully satisfied with e-resources provided by university libraries.

INTRODUCTION

Information has become wider in present day research, covering non-print materials. For research it is essential to use information in print as well as electronic information. Both are available in various sources crossing the boundaries of a specific library. Library and information centers are required to support teaching, learning and research by incorporating electronic and digital information and professional skills. The electronic resources have become a very widely used format of choice for academic library patrons as they offer today's users many

opportunities which was not available to their predecessors.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Agrapu (2013) found in their study that majority of research scholars have difficulties in using e-resources like low speed of internet, frequent power failure and very limited time to access. Baljinder (2009) the impact of e-resources was visible from the decrease in number of printed journals in comparison to the increase in number of electronic journals. The printed material is being quickly replaced by the electronic resources. Bhatt (2004) reported that consortia-

based subscription to electronic resources can help college and university libraries in order to enhance their access capacity to a large number of periodicals, yet there is a need to develop a policy for consortia-based subscription to electronic resources which should clearly indicate the terms and conditions favouring and protecting the academic interest of the college and university libraries. The study of Borrego (2007) disclosed that a high proportion of teaching and research staff are aware of the collection of electronic journals and that there is an increasing preference for the electronic to the detriment of the printed format.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the use of different types of electronic resource by the users.
- To study the purpose of the use of electronic resources by the users.
- To study the satisfaction and problems in utilizing the e-resources.
- Determine the awareness of e-resources among the users of University Library.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study area is limited to Gujarat State. The study will be limited to the university libraries which are included in the list of 2(F) and 12 (B) of the UGC Act 1956.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is focused on the PG students, academic and administrative staff of the nineteen universities of Gujarat State. The Stratified random sampling technique was used to choose the sample. Users were approached by through e-mails, visits to their respective departments as well as through respective university librarian. Several consistent follow up were made to obtain maximum response from the users.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Frequency to learn and handle of E-resources use

Details	Frequency	Percentage
Training from Uni. Library	154	20.4
Guidance from colleagues & friends	357	47.3
Self-Instruction	228	30.2
External course	4	0.5
Any other	0	0
Total	754	100

Result shows that 357 (47.3) % of the users are getting information on e-resources through colleagues & friends, 228 (30.2% of the user were getting information through self-instruction, 154 (20.4) % of the user get training from university library while only 4(0.5) % of the user who have done external courses for use of e-resources. So it's very clear that majority of the users were get guidance for using of e-resources through your colleagues and friends.

Table 2: Purpose of use of E-Resources

Purpose	Frequency	Percentage
Research	452	59.9
Teaching	247	32.7
Publication	13	1.7
Any Other	42	5.5
Total	754	100

The result Shows that 452 (59.9) % of the user use e-resources for Research work, 247 (32.7) for teaching purpose, 13 (1.7) for publication, while 42 (5.5) % user use e-resources for other purpose. The above analysis reveals that respondents of university libraries mostly use the e-resources for research and Teaching

Table 3: Awareness of UGC Infonet E-Journals consortia

Details	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	295	41
No	423	58.9
Total	718	100

All the universities do not have access of UGC INFONET consortium thus above result shows that only 295(41%) of respondents are aware of the UGC INFONET Consortium while 423 (58.9%) of the user are not aware of the consortium. The result reveals that majority of respondents do not know about the UGC Infonet E-Journal consortia.

Table 4: Use of UGC Infonet E-Journals Consortia

Details	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	201	29
No	490	70.9
Total	691	100

According to above table shows that 490(70.9%) of the respondents of university libraries do not use UGC INFONET consortia while 201 (29%) of the respondents use consortia journals. The above analysis indicated that majority of the respondents are not using UGC Infonet E-journal consortia.

Table 5: Place to use of E-Resources

Details	Frequency	Percentage
University Library	369	48.9
Dept. Library	228	30.2
At Home	155	20.5
Other Place	2	0.2
Total	754	100

The finding shows that 2 (0.2%) user use e-resources at other place, 155 (20.5%) use e-resource at home, 228 (30.2%) use Dept. Library and 369 (48.9%) users use e-resource at university library. Finally we can conclude that most of the users use e-resources at university library and departmental library.

Table 6: Problem faces while using the E-Resources

Details	Frequency	Percentage
Slow access speed	195	28.1
Overload of information on the internet	218	31.3
Difficulty in finding relevant information	198	28.4
It takes too long to view/download pages	42	6
Privacy problem	34	4.8
Any other please specify	9	1.2
Total	696	100

According to the above table shows that respondents of university that 218 (31.3%) information on the Internet while 198 (28.4%) said that they face difficulty in finding relevant information, 195 (28.1%) users opined that face slow access speed while searching E-resources, 42 (4.8%) said that it takes too long to view pages, 34 (4.8%) user face a privacy problem and 9 (1.2%) user other problems while searching the E-resources. Majority of the respondent face three types of problem Overload information on the Internet, Difficulty in finding in relevant and slow access speed while searching the E-resources.

Table 7: Satisfaction of E-Resources provided by University Library

Details	Frequency	Percentage
Fully	209	27.7
Partially	353	46.8
Least Satisfied	136	18
No comments	52	6.8
Total	754	100

Above result shows that 353(46.8) % users feel that they were partially satisfied while 209 (27.7) % users are fully satisfied, 136 (18) % of the user are Least Satisfied and 52(6.8) % users are have chosen “no comments” option of the above answer. The overall opinion of the library respondents is that only one third users are fully satisfied with e-resource provided by university.

Table 8: Required training programme for accessing of E-Resources

Details	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	687	91.1
No	67	8.8
Total	754	100

The Above result shows that 687 (91.1%) Majority of the respondents are required training programme for accessing of E-resources while 67 (8.8%) user opined that they no need training programme for access of E-resources.

CONCLUSION

The University libraries need to pay due attention for making establishment for well-planned electronic resource-based services to its end-users. The library should offer more facilities for e-resources to keep up to date of the users. Announcements should be done by the library about the accessibility of new e-resources of library users. Library should provide the facilities for the users to get acquainted with e-resources subscribed by the library. Special training programs should be organized for the library user for the maximum use of e-resources so that users can effectively trace relevant information. The virtual reference services and e-document services need to be provided to the end users.

REFERENCES

- Agrapu, D. (2013). *Collection Management of Electronic Information Resources: An Analytical Study of Selected University*. Andhra University.
- Baljinder, K. A. (2009). Use of Electronic Information Resources A Case Study of Thapar University. *Desidoc Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 29(2), 67-73.
- Bhatt, R. K. (2004). University Libraries in India and Electronic Journals: The Role of Consortia-based Subscription of E-journals for the Effective Use of Financial Resources. *2nd International CALIBER-2004*. New Delhi.
- Dadzie, P. (2005). Electronic Resources: Access and usage at Asheshi University College. *Campus wide Information System*, 22(5), 290-297.
- Golian, L. (2000). Utilizing Internet resources by Educational professionals in the new Millennium. *Information Technology and Libraries*, pp. 136-143.
- Herring, S. D. (2002). Use of Electronic Resources of Scholarly Electronic Journals: A Citation Analysis. *College and Research Libraries*, 334-340.
- Mathew, S. A. (2005). Use of E-resources in A Networked Environment: A Case Study of CUSAT. *National Convention on Library and Information Networking (NACLIN)*, (p. 291).
- Nikam, K. A. (2007, March). Use of E-Journals and databases by the Academic community of University of Mysore: A Survey. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, pp. 19-22.
- S, V. G. (2010). E-Resources of Information: A Study of attitudes of Research Schoolars. *CALIBER 2007*. Chandigarh: Panjab University.
- (2013). Retrieved from <http://www.ugc.ac.in>. 60th Annual Report 2013-14. New Delhi:University GrantsCommmission.
- (2014). Retrieved from <http://gujarat-education.gov.in/higher/universities/html>.
- (2014). Retrieved from <https://www.shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>.
- (2015). Retrieved from <http://www.doaj.org>
- (2015). Retrieved from <http://www.jgateplus.com>